

Tuning of Molecular Plasmons in Anthracene by Peripheral Functionalization

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: A term “molecular plasmon” was recently introduced to describe collective, coherent excitations in polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). In spite of significant practical implications of molecular plasmons, experimental studies demonstrating how their properties can be controlled are currently limited. Here we report first experimental study of the effect of a systematic peripheral functionalization in a series of synthesized anthracene derivatives on the energy and extent of plasmonic character of their electronic excitations. Spectroscopically observed electronic excitations in electrochemically charged anthracene derivatives are analyzed in terms of several molecular plasmonicity metrics using Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TDDFT). We show that the energy and the degree of plasmonicity of the electronic excitations vary systematically with the position and type of the peripheral functionalization. We explain the origin of these variations and outline how targeted functionalization can be used to tune the plasmonic response of linear PAHs.

KEYWORDS: Molecular plasmonics • Anthracene • Acenes • Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons • Spectro-Electrochemistry • TDDFT

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons consisting of two or more fused benzene rings (PAHs) have been a subject of research interest for about two centuries¹⁻⁴ due to their intriguing chemistry,^{5,6} unusual combination of electrical and optical properties⁷ as well their potential environmental impact^{8,9} and carcinogenicity. More recently, PAHs have attracted a renewed interest inspired by studies indicating that their electronic excitations, traditionally thought of as single-electron transitions between π and π^* orbitals, can in fact be collective in nature.¹⁰⁻¹³ These collective electronic excitations, termed “molecular plasmons”, involve coherent displacements of electron densities in a fashion resembling light-induced oscillations of surface electrons in metal nanoparticles, known as localized surface plasmon resonance.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ While understanding of the molecular plasmon phenomenon is still evolving, growing number of studies support the notion that PAHs and other small molecules can support optical excitations with plasmonic characteristics.^{10-13,17-22} Better understanding of and ability to control molecular plasmons promises to yield intriguing opportunities for their exploitation in electronics, photonics, medicine and other fields.²³⁻²⁷

An appealing feature of the plasmon resonance effect in metal nanoparticles is that the energies of the plasmon resonances can often be tuned across UV, VIS and NIR spectral ranges by changes in the size and shape of the nanoparticle.²⁸⁻³⁰ Similarly, the energies of electronic excitations in PAHs extend from UV to NIR spectral ranges, depending on

the PAH size.³¹⁻³³ However, practical exploitation of this tunability is often difficult due to the challenges with the preparation of larger PAHs and their limited chemical and photochemical stability.^{31,34-36}

Here we investigate the effect of systematic peripheral functionalization of anthracene with methyl ester carboxylate (MEC) functional group (**Scheme 1**), on the energy and the extent of the molecular plasmonic character of excitations in its anion radical. The details of the syntheses of the derivatives, the NMR spectra of all the products and

Scheme 1. Chemical structures of the compounds studied in this work. (1) anthracene, (2) dimethyl anthracene-1,8-dicarboxylate, (3) methyl anthracene-9-carboxylate, (4) dimethyl anthracene-9,10-dicarboxylate, (5) dimethyl anthracene-2,6-dicarboxylate.

Figure 1. (a) Electronic absorption spectra of anthracenes in acetonitrile. The high (<300nm) and low (>300 nm) energy regions are characterized by $\pi - \pi^*$ transitions with the transition dipole oriented along the long (${}^1A \rightarrow {}^1B_b$) and short (${}^1A \rightarrow {}^1L_a$) molecular axes, respectively. (b) Cyclic voltammograms (CV) for one electron reduction of anthracenes in 0.1 M TBAPF₆, 1-4 (5mM) in Acetonitrile (ACN) and 5 (~2mM) in THF. WE; Pt disk, RE: 10mM Ag/AgNO₃ in 0.1M TBAPF₆ (ACN) and CE: Pt wire.

characterization methods are summarized in the Supporting Information (SI).

Fig. 1(a) shows the electronic absorption spectra of compounds (1) to (5) in acetonitrile. The spectra are characterized by two groups of absorption bands, one in the region 220-280 nm and the second in the region 300-420 nm. The higher energy absorption is dominated by a sharp peak with a molar extinction coefficient of $\sim 100,000 - 180,000 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$. The vibronically structured peaks in the lower energy region have significantly lower extinction coefficients with values in the range $\sim 4,000 - 8,000 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$. The main characteristics of the absorption spectra for all the compounds are summarized in **Table 1**.

According to Platt. et. al.,³⁷ the two sets of the absorption bands, attributed to the $\pi - \pi^*$ electronic excitations, can be categorized in terms of the excited states involved and the orientation of the transition dipole with respect to the molecular axis. In Platt's notation, the experimentally observed high energy excitation is labeled ${}^1A \rightarrow {}^1B_b$, while the low energy excitation is labeled ${}^1A \rightarrow {}^1L_a$. Here the symbol A refers

to the ground state, symbols B and L to high and low energy excited states, respectively and the superscript refers to the multiplicity (1 = singlet) of the state. The subscripts "a" and "b" refer to the transverse and longitudinal orientation of the transition dipole, respectively.

Fig. 1(b) shows the cyclic voltammograms (CVs) of compounds (1) to (5) recorded at potentials negative relative to Standard Hydrogen Electrode (SHE). In all cases distinct cathodic peaks were observed in the range -1.0 to -2.0 V vs NHE, attributed to a single electron reduction. While the CVs are fully reversible in the case of compounds (1), (2) and (5), they are irreversible (as indicated by the absence of the anodic wave) for (3) and (4). The irreversibility is attributed to the formation of a reactive radical anion, which can disproportionate to the peripheral functional group and/or become susceptible to a radical - radical coupling between neighboring anions to yield a dimer dianion, as shown in **Scheme S5** in SI.^{38, 39} This reaction is less efficient in the case of (1), (2) and (5) because the peripheral functional group is either lacking or is spatially isolated from the

Table 1. Experimentally observed electronic absorption and redox characteristics of neutral and charged anthracenes.

An	$A_{0,h}^a$ (nm/eV)	$\epsilon_{0,h}^a$ ($\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) $\times 10^{-3}$	$A_{0,l}^a$ (nm/eV)	$\epsilon_{0,l}^a$ ($\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) $\times 10^{-3}$	$E_{1,red}^0$ (V vs. NHE)	$E_{1,ox}^0$ (V vs. NHE)	E_{mid}^0 (V vs. NHE)	A_{-1}^d (nm/eV)	ϵ_{-1}^d ($\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$) $\times 10^{-3}$
1	252/4.92	178.8 ± 8.9	376/3.30	7.03 ± 0.35	-1.77 ± 0.03	1.45 ± 0.02	-0.16 ± 0.03	727/1.71	4.41 ± 0.10
2	255/4.86	94.7 ± 4.7	403/3.08	5.04 ± 0.25	-1.29 ± 0.02	1.68 ± 0.02	0.20 ± 0.02	600/2.06 1138/1.09	1.85 ± 0.02 4.28 ± 0.10
3	253/4.90	149.0 ± 7.5	381/3.25	5.950 ± 0.30	-1.39 ± 0.02	1.56 ± 0.02	0.09 ± 0.02	534/2.32	-
4	254/4.88	151.5 ± 7.6	385/3.22	7.240 ± 0.35	-1.21 ± 0.01	1.80 ± 0.02	0.30 ± 0.02	509/2.44	-
5	272/4.55	167.3 ± 8.4	409/3.03	4.250 ± 0.20	-1.27 ± 0.02	- ^e	-	798/1.55	7.82 ± 0.85

^a Peak energy (in nm/eV) and the molar extinction coefficients of the high-energy ($A_{0,h}$, $\epsilon_{0,h}$) and the low-energy ($A_{0,l}$, $\epsilon_{0,l}$) electronic transitions in the absorption spectra of investigated neutral anthracenes. ^b Standard reduction potentials for the first reduction ($E_{1,red}^0$) and oxidation ($E_{1,ox}^0$) of investigated anthracenes. ^c Midgap energy defined as $E_{mid}^0 = (E_{1,red}^0 + E_{1,ox}^0)/2$. ^d Wavelength (in nm) and energy (in eV) and the molar extinction coefficients (A_{-1} , ϵ_{-1}) of the low energy electronic transitions in the absorption spectra of investigated singly charged anthracenes. ^e The oxidation potential was not determined due to the poor solubility of the derivative in acetonitrile and limited potential window of THF.

radical anion. To minimize the impact of the side reactions, the first reduction ($E_{1,red}^0$) and oxidation ($E_{1,ox}^0$) potentials of all derivatives, summarized in **Table 1**, were determined by a Differential Pulse Voltammetry (DPV) (see SI for details). Also included is a mid-gap energy defined as $E_{mid}^0 = (E_{1,red}^0 + E_{1,ox}^0)/2$.

Fig. 2(a-e) shows the electronic absorption spectra of the low energy, ${}^1A \rightarrow {}^1L_a$ transitions for the neutral anthracenes (gray traces), compared with the electronic absorption spectra of their anion radicals (green traces). The

absorption spectra of the radical anions were obtained in a spectro-electrochemistry experiment with an optically transparent Sn-doped Indium oxide (ITO) used as a working electrode (see SI for details). The changes in the absorption spectra of the reduced anthracenes were recorded following a step to a potential ~ 0.2 V more negative than $E_{1,red}^0$ for a given derivative. The changes in the optical properties upon formation of the anion radicals were visible by a naked eye on the surface of the ITO (see **Fig. 2(f-j)**). We note that the blue color of anion radical $(2)^{-1}$ is attributed to the

Figure 2. (a-e) Experimentally measured electronic absorption spectra of neutral (gray traces) and negatively charged (green traces) anthracenes (1) to (5), respectively. The charged anthracenes were generated electrochemically by holding the potential of the ITO electrode ~ 0.2 V negative of the first reduction potential ($E_{1,red}^0$) for a given anthracene (see Table 1). The red dashed traces show the theoretically (IMDHO) calculated vibrationally resolved electronic absorption spectra of the negatively charged anthracenes. (f-j) photographs of the ITO electrodes before (0) and during (-1) application of the corresponding potential. (k-o) Calculated energies of the molecular orbitals (H = HOMO, L = LUMO) for the neutral and singly negatively charged anthracenes (1) to (5). Electronic transitions contributing the most to the low energy absorption band in the anion radical are indicated by green dashed arrows. The energies of the MOs were calculated at the TDDFT B3LYP/631g+(d) level of theory.

excitation at 2.11 eV, not the lowest energy excitation at 1.18 eV. The latter by itself would appear colorless as this absorption is located in the NIR part of the spectrum. Also, the orange color observed for anion radical $(\mathbf{4})^{-1}$ is attributed to the excitation at 2.46 eV, not the lowest energy excitation at 1.99 eV. The latter by itself would likely appear red. The positions of the maxima (A_{-1}) of the low energy absorption bands of anion radicals observed in the VIS and NIR spectral ranges are summarized in **Table 1**. The molar extinction coefficients (ϵ_{-1}) of the absorption bands were determined by chrono-coulometry measurements (see SI for details).

To better understand the origin of the main features in the absorption spectra of the neutral and charged anthracenes, we performed TDDFT calculations of their electronic structure at the B3LYP/631g+(d) level of theory (see SI for details). The calculated energies of the frontier and adjacent molecular orbitals (MOs) are graphically summarized in **Fig. 2k-o**. As shown in the figure, charging of the anthracenes leads to dramatic distortions of their electronic structure. First, the addition of a single electron leads to splitting of the orbital spin degeneracy, whereby the MOs form two different manifolds, labeled here as α and β . Second, in both manifolds HOMO and LUMO shift to more negative energies vs. NHE. Third, the energy separation between the HOMO and LUMO orbitals (the HOMO-LUMO gap) is significantly reduced in both manifolds.

The results of the TDDFT calculations also allowed us to identify electronic transitions contributing the most to the low energy bands in the absorption spectra of the anion radicals. These transitions are indicated by the green arrows in the diagrams shown in **Fig 2, k-o** and included in **Table 2**. For example, in anthracene $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$, the lowest energy absorption band is mostly attributed to the $H_{\alpha} \rightarrow (L+1)_{\alpha}$ and $H_{\beta} \rightarrow$

L_{β} electronic transitions. In the case of $(\mathbf{4})^{-1}$, the lowest energy absorption is attributed mostly to the $H_{\beta} \rightarrow L_{\beta}$ and $H_{\alpha} \rightarrow (L+2)_{\alpha}$ transitions. To more quantitatively compare how well the calculated electronic structure correlates with the experiment, for the lowest energy transitions we performed calculations of the vibrationally resolved absorption spectra by the independent mode displaced harmonic oscillator (IMDHO) method in Orca.⁴⁰ The calculated, vibrationally-resolved absorption bands, shown as red dashed lines in **Fig 2**, panels a-e, are in a good agreement with the experimental data (green solid lines).

Results summarized in **Fig. 2a-e** and **Table 1** show that the peak position of the low energy absorption band of the anion radicals of the derivatives shift either to higher $(\mathbf{3})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{4})^{-1}$ or lower energies $(\mathbf{2})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$ relative to $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$, depending on the position of the functional group. As a result, across the series, the lowest energy transitions vary from 2.4 eV for $(\mathbf{4})^{-1}$ all the way to the NIR range, 1.18 eV for $(\mathbf{2})^{-1}$. The significant variations in the energies of the lowest energy excitations in the anion radicals are attributed primarily to the differences in the molecular structure of the anion radicals. While the derivatives $(\mathbf{2})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$ form nearly planar structures with MEC groups fully conjugated with the anthracene core, the derivatives $(\mathbf{3})^{-1}$ and $(\mathbf{4})^{-1}$ form nonplanar structures, which leads to a broadening of the HOMO-LUMO gap. See section 5.7 of the SI for more details. The above analysis allows us now to systematically examine the plasmonic character of the excitations in $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$ to $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$.

Over the past decade, number of approaches was proposed for quantifying the extent of plasmonic character of molecular excitations.^{12, 17-19, 41-44} Here we will focus on quantifying the plasmonic character of the excitations in the radicals $(\mathbf{1})^{-1}$ to $(\mathbf{5})^{-1}$ in terms of two previously proposed

Table 2. Calculated electronic structure, redox and plasmonic characteristics of neutral and charged anthracenes.

An	$A_{0,f}^a$ (eV)	$E_{1,red}^b$ (V)	$E_{1,ox}^b$ (V)	E_{mid}^c (V)	A_{-1}^d (eV)	Osc. str. ^e	A_{-1}^f assign.	N^g	$t.d.m.^h$ x/y/z (a.u.)	Pf^i (a.u.)	E_{plas}^j (a.u.) x1000	$Itds^k$ (a.u.) x1000	$mGPI^l$ (a.u.)	Osc. str. x $mGPI$
1	3.17	-1.64	1.47	-0.09	1.91	0.186	$H_{\alpha} \rightarrow (L+1)_{\alpha} + \dots$	3	-2.00/0.00/0.00	1806	10.63	1.34	7.93	1.47
					2.21	0.023	$H_{\beta} \rightarrow L_{\beta} + \dots$	3	0.00/0.65/0.00	311	8.21	1.61	5.09	0.12
2	2.95	-1.06	1.78	0.36	1.18	0.169	$H_{\alpha} \rightarrow L_{\alpha} + \dots$	2	-2.42/0.00/0.16	2793	12.40	1.24	9.97	1.68
					2.11	0.024	$H_{\beta} \rightarrow L_{\beta} + \dots$	3	0.00/0.68/0.00	371	5.61	1.12	5.01	0.12
3	3.09	-1.27	1.64	0.19	2.26	0.113	$H_{\beta} \rightarrow L_{\beta} + \dots$	4	0.40/1.37/-0.14	1130	11.11	1.47	7.54	0.85
					2.40	0.116	$H_{\alpha} \rightarrow L_{\alpha} + \dots$	3	-1.36/0.35/-0.06	1254	6.75	1.01	6.70	0.78
4	3.03	-1.05	1.79	0.37	1.99	0.025	$H_{\beta} \rightarrow L_{\beta} + \dots$	2	0.01/0.72/0.01	275	7.19	1.69	4.26	0.11
					2.46	0.216	$H_{\alpha} \rightarrow (L+2)_{\alpha} + \dots$	4	-0.35/1.86/0.01	1700	9.93	1.36	7.31	1.58
5	2.86	-1.19	1.96	0.39	1.59	0.424	$H_{\alpha} \rightarrow L_{\alpha} + \dots$	3	-3.14/-1.01/0.00	3792	13.66	1.38	9.92	4.21
					2.09	0.099	$H_{\beta} \rightarrow L_{\beta} + \dots$	4	-1.35/0.33/0.00	815	8.22	1.40	5.88	0.58

^aEnergy of the low energy electronic transition in the neutral anthracenes (not vibrationally resolved). ^bStandard potentials for the first reduction ($E_{1,red}^b$) and oxidation ($E_{1,ox}^b$) of the anthracene. ^cMidgap energy $E_{mid}^c = (E_{1,red}^b + E_{1,ox}^b)/2$ of the neutral anthracene. All potentials are shown relative to standard hydrogen electrode (SHE). ^dPeak energy of the lowest energy absorption (not vibrationally resolved) in anion radical. ^eOscillator strength of the excitation. ^fElectronic transition contributing the most to the lowest energy absorption band in the anion radical. ^gNumber of contributing electronic transitions with orbital transition coefficient larger than 0.1. ^hTransition dipole matrix. To convert a.u. (atomic units) to SI units, multiply by 8.478×10^{-30} C.m. ⁱPlasmonicity index defined by Eq. (1) in the main text. To convert to SI units, multiply by 3.63×10^{-9} J²m⁶/C². ^jPlasmonic energy defined in Eq.(2). To convert to eV or Joules multiply by 27.21 eV or by 4.34×10^{-18} J, respectively. ^kIntegrated transition density squared shown as denominator in Eqs. (1) and (3). To convert to SI units multiply by 3.27×10^{-17} C²m⁻³. ^lModified General Plasmonicity Index defined by Eq. (3). To convert to SI units, multiply by 0.28 nm².

metrics: Plasmonicity Index, PI , and Generalized Plasmonicity Index, GPI .

First introduced by Bursi et al.,⁴¹ the PI is defined as:

$$PI(\omega_I) \approx \frac{\int |v_{ind,I}(r)|^2 d^3r}{\int |\rho_I(r)|^2 d^3r} = \frac{\int \left| \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int \frac{\rho_I(r')}{|r-r'|} d^3r' \right|^2 d^3r}{\int |\rho_I(r)|^2 d^3r} \quad (1),$$

where ρ_I is the transition charge density of an excitation I , at the excitation frequency ω_I and $v_{ind,I}(r)$ is the Coulomb potential induced by the charge density redistribution. (Note, in atomic units $4\pi\epsilon_0 = 1$). Other forms of Eq. (1) have been also proposed where the induced Coulomb potential is normalized by factors other than the integrated square of transition charge density.⁴¹

In a subsequent work, Zhang et al.⁴² noted several limitations of the PI , including its dependence on the size of the studied system and the observation that for small systems with weak plasmonic signals, the PI may fail to identify plasmonic resonances. The calculation of the PI also presents practical computational problem due to the diffuse character of the induced Coulomb potential $v_{ind,I}(r)$ (see SI). In part, to address the limitations of PI , Zhang et al.⁴² introduced a new metric, GPI , which at plasmon resonance frequency, ω_I , of an electronic excitation I , is defined as:

$$GPI(\omega_I) \approx \frac{E_{plas,I}}{\Gamma_I} = \frac{\int v_{ind,I}(r) \rho_I(r') d^3r d^3r'}{\Gamma_I} = \frac{\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \int \int \frac{\rho_I(r) \rho_I(r')}{|r-r'|} d^3r d^3r'}{\Gamma_I} \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2) $E_{plas,I}$ is plasmonic energy, a Coulomb self-interaction energy of a transition charge density of the excitation I , Γ_I is a damping energy of the plasmonic oscillation, a quantity related to the rate, k , of the energy loss of the collective oscillation via dephasing processes ($\Gamma = \hbar k$) and ρ_I is a transition charge density of an electronic excitation I . Thus, GPI is a dimensionless quantity that measures the extent of plasmonic character of an oscillation as a Coulomb self-interaction energy (unlike potential in PI), normalized by the damping energy of that excitation.

One of the challenges in calculating the GPI of an excitation is quantification of the damping energy, Γ . In the original work the authors used a phenomenological approach, where Γ was assumed to be a constant in the range 25 to 120 meV, depending on the studied system. Similar approach was adopted in more recent studies of optical excitations in molecular J -aggregates⁴⁵ and peropyrene and its derivatives.⁴⁶ A more quantitative approach requires theoretical analysis of the relaxation rate for each excitation. Alternatively, Γ can, in principle, be determined from experiment, since $\Gamma = 2\Delta E$, where ΔE is the full width at half of the maximum (FWHM) of the Lorentzian profile of a plasmon peak.⁴² In an effort to quantify the Γ values for the excitations in anion radicals studied here, we analyzed the shapes of the bands in their absorption spectra. As can be seen in **Fig. 2a-e**, the absorption spectra of all anions at energies above ~ 2.5 eV are distorted by significant spectral overlaps. However, in the spectra of **(1)⁻¹**, **(2)⁻¹** and **(5)⁻¹** a group of isolated bands, with well-resolved vibronic features is observed in the low energy, $\sim 1.0 - 2.5$ eV, region (see **Fig. 2a, b, e**). We analyzed these isolated bands by numerical fitting using Voigt spectral profiles (see SI). Although we were able to obtain estimates of the damping energy for several isolated excitations, determination of Γ for all excitations across the series of compounds or even within the same

compound was not possible due to significant spectral overlaps and heterogeneous broadening. Therefore, in the assessment of the extent of plasmonicity in terms of GPI , here we report only the calculated values of $E_{plas,I}$ (see **Table 2**).

To more quantitatively compare the plasmonic character of excitations in the anion radicals **(1)⁻¹** to **(5)⁻¹**, here we propose an alternative metric, which we call a modified GPI , or $mGPI$, defined as:

$$mGPI(\omega_I) \approx 4\pi\epsilon_0 \frac{E_{plas,I}}{\int |\rho_I(r)|^2 d^3r} = \frac{\int \frac{\rho_I(r) \rho_I(r')}{|r-r'|} d^3r d^3r'}{\int |\rho_I(r)|^2 d^3r} \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (3) ϵ_0 is permittivity of vacuum and the remaining terms have the same meaning as in Eqs. (1) and (2). The normalization of the $E_{plas,I}$ by the integral of the square of the transition charge density removes its trivial dependence on a system size as the integral accounts for the participation volume (size) of the corresponding excitation. The multiplication term $4\pi\epsilon_0$ is introduced to simplify the units of $mGPI$ in the SI unit system. The term has no effect on the value of $mGPI$ in atomic units. All terms in Eq. (3) can be obtained from DFT calculations. To test whether the $mGPI$ correctly reflects the degree of plasmonic character of excitations, we calculated $mGPI$ values for excitations in Ag₂₀ cluster as well as neutral anthracenes (see SI, sec. 5.9). We found that the results are in a good qualitative agreement with the conclusions of earlier studies.

Fig. 3a-e shows the calculated $mGPI$ values for the excitations in the anthracene radicals **(1)⁻¹** to **(5)⁻¹** in the energy range 0.7 to 4.0 eV. In the figure, the values of $mGPI$ shown as vertical red bars are overlaid with TDDFT calculated (not vibrationally resolved) absorption spectra of the anion radicals (green traces) and neutral anthracenes (gray traces). For clarity, the red bars are shown only for excitations with oscillator strength larger than 0.015. In the plots, the calculated $mGPI$ values were normalized to the highest overall $mGPI$ value found for the electronic excitation at 3.39 eV in **(1)⁻¹**. The results summarized in **Fig. 3a-e** show that all excitations in the 0.7 to 4.0 eV energy range have some plasmonic character, ranging from $\sim 25\%$ to 100% on the relative scale. When comparing different anthracenes, the results show that for anion radicals **(1)⁻¹**, **(3)⁻¹** and **(4)⁻¹** the excitations with the most plasmonic character lie in the UV spectral region at energies above ~ 3.4 eV. In contrast, for anion radicals **(2)⁻¹** and **(5)⁻¹** the most plasmonic excitations are observed in the VIS-NIR spectral range, below 1.6 eV.

Calculated values of $mGPI$, PI and E_{plas} for the two of the lowest energy excitations for each anion radical are summarized in **Table 2** (a more complete list is included in Table S8 in SI). The results in **Table 2** show, that in the region $\sim 1.0 - 2.5$ eV, the excitations with the highest $mGPI$ values are found at 1.91 eV in **(1)⁻¹**, 1.18 eV in **(2)⁻¹** and 1.59 eV in **(5)⁻¹**. The excitations with the lowest $mGPI$ values are found at 1.99 eV in **(4)⁻¹** and 2.11 eV in **(2)⁻¹**. As may be expected, the calculated values of PI and E_{plas} follow a similar trend, but there are notable differences. Perhaps the most remarkable is the dramatic variability of the PI values of the low energy excitations relative to much more moderate changes in the E_{plas} and $mGPI$ values. We attribute this to the squaring of the induced Coulomb potential in the expression for the PI (Eq. 1), making it very sensitive to small changes in the transition density.

Considering the $mGPI$ s of the individual excitations and their corresponding oscillator strengths (within the context of overall weak plasmonic character of the excitations stud

Figure 3. TDDFT calculated electronic absorption spectra (not vibrationally resolved) of the neutral (gray traces) and singly charged (green traces) anthracenes. The $mGPI$ values for all compounds were normalized to the highest calculated $mGPI$ value, corresponding to the 3.39 eV excitation in anion radical $(1)^{-}$. The values of the y-axes pertain to $mGPI$ plots. Panels (f-j) show the transition density of the corresponding transitions of the neutral and charged anthracenes. See main text for more details.

ied here) we can roughly divide the excitations into three categories: 1.) “bright, strongly plasmonic”; high oscillator strengths and high plasmonicity; example: $H_{\alpha} \rightarrow L_{\alpha}$ excitation in anion radical $(5)^{-}$ at 1.59 eV; 2.) “moderately bright, strongly plasmonic”; moderate oscillator strengths, but a significant plasmonicity; example: $H_{\alpha} \rightarrow L_{\alpha}$ excitation in anion

radical $(2)^{-}$ at 1.18 eV; 3) “dark, weakly plasmonic”; small oscillator strengths and weak plasmonic character; example: $H_{\beta} \rightarrow L_{\beta}$ transitions in $(1)^{-}$, $(2)^{-}$ and $(4)^{-}$ at 2.21, 2.11 and 1.99 eV, respectively. The bright, strongly plasmonic and dark, weakly plasmonic excitations can be readily identified as the excitations with the largest and smallest

products of the oscillator strength and the $mGPI$ (see the right most column in **Table 2**).

Further insights into the origin of the observed variations in the degree of plasmonicity of the excitations can be gained by inspection of the corresponding transition charge density maps. In **Fig. 3f-j** we show the transition charge density maps for the lowest energy excitations in the neutral anthracenes (**1**) to (**5**) and two low energy excitations in the anion radicals (**1**)⁻¹ to (**5**)⁻¹. To accurately represent the collective nature of the excitations, 3D charge density maps were generated using an overlay option available in Gaussian 16 software package.⁴⁷ This option includes in the map all electronic transitions involved in a given excitation. The visualization was done using Vesta software package.⁴⁸

As shown in the figure, in the neutral form, in all compounds, the transition dipoles for the lowest energy (HOMO-LUMO) transitions are polarized primarily along the transverse (short) molecular axis (¹A→¹L_a in Platt notation). A greater transfer of electron density along the short molecular axis is observed in compounds (**2**), (**3**) and (**4**). This results in a red shift of their low energy absorption bands relative to anthracene (**1**) (see **Fig. 1a**). These excitations are mostly single electron HOMO-LUMO transitions and have a weak plasmonic character ($mGPI \leq 5.4$, see Table S8).

In anthracene anions, where the introduction of charge leads to splitting of orbital spin degeneracy into two manifolds, the situation is more complex. In (**1**)⁻¹, (**2**)⁻¹ and (**5**)⁻¹ the lowest energy excitations, which are part of the alpha manifold, are polarized primarily along the longitudinal (long) molecular axis. In contrast, in (**3**)⁻¹ and (**4**)⁻¹ the lowest energy excitations take place within the beta manifold and are primarily polarized along the transverse axis. This qualitative observation is more quantitatively conveyed in the x- and y-component values of transition density matrices (t.d.m.) summarized in **Table 2**. Relating this observation to the magnitudes of the $mGPI$ summarized in **Fig. 3a-e** and **Table 2** reveals that $mGPI$ values are consistently higher for the excitations polarized along the longitudinal axis, which take place within the alpha manifold. Since the lowest energy excitations take place within the alpha manifold only in derivatives (**2**)⁻¹ and (**5**)⁻¹ this suggests that such excitations are favored by functionalization of anthracene with MEC groups in 1,8 and 2,6 positions. As discussed above, this functionalization leads to stabilization of frontier MOs within the alpha manifold thanks to the electron withdrawing induction and mesomeric effects of the MEC groups, enabled by their planarization into the plane of anthracene, following the one electron reduction (see **Fig. 4a**). Thus, this stabilization not only induces shifts of the low energy excitations towards the NIR region, relative to anthracene, but it also facilitates polarization of these excitations along the longitudinal molecular axis, which increases their plasmonic character (**Fig. 4b**).

Interestingly, when comparing the lowest energy excitation in anthracene anion radical (**1**)⁻¹(1.91 eV) with the corresponding excitations in derivatives (**2**)⁻¹(1.18 eV) and (**5**)⁻¹(1.59 eV), we find that the $mGPI$ values are considerably (~25%) higher for the derivatives relative to the anthracene (see **Table 2**). At the same time, the integrated squares of transition densities ($Itds$ in **Table 2**) for these excitations are comparable. This suggests that in spite of the differences in molecular size, the participation volumes of the excitations are similar. This means that the enhancement of the

Figure 4. (a) Schematic diagram of the changes in the molecular structure and electron density distribution in (**2**) and (**2**)⁻¹ upon electrochemical charging with a single electron. MESP = molecular electrostatic potential. (b) A schematic summary of the effects of the peripheral functionalization on the energies, oscillator strengths and relative $mGPI$ (in atomic units, a.u.) of the low energy excitations in (**1**)⁻¹, (**2**)⁻¹ and (**5**)⁻¹.

$mGPI$ is not a result of a trivial increase in the size of the derivatives, but rather it is a result of inherent enhancement of the plasmonic character of the excitations. In contrast, the $mGPI$ values of the lowest energy excitations in derivatives (**3**)⁻¹ (2.26 eV) and (**4**)⁻¹ (1.99 eV) are lower by ~5% and ~50%, respectively, compared to anthracene. The $Itds$ values are in both cases higher and the $E_{plas,l}$ lower than in the case of anthracene. This indicates that these excitations are more localized and less plasmonic than the corresponding excitation in anthracene.

To better understand these results, we calculated the $mGPI$, $E_{plas,l}$ and $Itds$ for anthracene anion radical functionalized in positions -9 (derivative (**6**)⁻¹), -1,8 and 2,6 with methyl functional groups. The results summarized in Table S8 in SI show that the calculated values for all methyl derivatives are nearly identical with those calculated for the 1.91 eV excitation in the anthracene anion radical. This shows that it is not just the position of the substitution, but also the type of the functional group that plays a role in determining the plasmonic character of an excitation. More specifically, the above results lead to following conclusions: 1.) Functional groups, which thanks to a planarization effectively conjugate with the core rings of the anthracene anion radical (e.g., MEC in positions -1,8 and -2,6) enhance the plasmonic character of the low energy excitations; 2.) Functional groups, which do not electronically conjugate with the anthracene core (e.g., methyl groups), do not significantly affect the plasmonic character of the low energy excitations, regardless of the position of the functionalization; 3.) Functional groups, which promote the polarization of the transition dipole along the transverse axis (e.g., MEC in positions -9 and -9,10) reduce the plasmonic character of the

low energy excitations primarily due to the increased localization of the excitation.

Finally, we note that based on the analysis of the transition dipole matrices, in all studied derivatives, the two lowest excitations have different charge transfer polarizations; one along the longitudinal and one along the transverse molecular axis. For example, in (2)⁻¹ the lowest energy excitation at 1.18 eV is primarily polarized along the longitudinal axis while the excitation at 2.11 eV is mainly polarized along the transverse axis (see **Table 2** and **Fig. 3g**). Similarly, in (3)⁻¹ the lowest energy excitation at 2.26 eV is mainly polarized along the transverse axis while the excitation at 2.40 eV is mainly⁴⁹ polarized along the longitudinal axis. This behavior of anthracene derivatives is similar to the asymmetric metal nanoparticles, such as gold nanorods. These nanostructures exhibit distinct resonances associated with the plasmon polarization along the transverse and longitudinal axes. The energy and relative strength of these plasmon resonances can be tuned by variations in the nanorod aspect (length:width) ratio,³⁰ in a fashion resembling the effect of peripheral functionalization on the plasmon response of the anthracene anion radicals.

Overall, our results show that peripheral functionalization can be used as an effective tool for tuning properties of molecular plasmons in linear PAHs.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Synthesis details of the Anthracene ester derivatives, Characterization (NMR and Mass spectrometry, optical absorption properties of neutral and Anion radical species), Electrochemistry and Spectro-electrochemistry methods, electrochemistry results (DPV), Quantification of plasmonicity, additional DFT results (redox potentials, Molecular orbitals of anion radical and molecular structures & ESP of neutral and anion radical), Estimation Damping energy of anion radical (1)⁻¹ and (5)⁻¹. mGPI summary of Ag₂₀ and anthracene derivatives. NMR data. (PDF). The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://>

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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